

Table 2. Performance of some elite lines in AICRIP trials under direct seeded rainfed upland conditions in India in 1982 and 1983 wet season.

Location	Yield (t/ha)					CD 0.05	Wet season rainfall (mm)
	NDR84	NDR85	NDR118 ^a	Akashi	Cauvery		
<i>1982</i>							
Faizabad, Uttar Pradesh	5.2	4.8	5.4	4.6	3.5	0.7	1082
Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh	4.1	4.6	5.4	4.2	4.0	1.2	851
Nagina, Uttar Pradesh	4.6	3.8	5.4	1.2	4.3	1.2	948
Ranchi, Bihar	1.7	2.8	5.4	1.2	1.9	0.8	794
Hazaribagh, Bihar	3.1	2.6	5.4	2.9	2.8	0.5	774
Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh	4.5	4.3	5.4	3.9	4.4	1.2	—
Jeypore, Orissa	3.4	5.1	5.4	3.0	1.2	1.5	1417
Mean	3.8	4.0	5.4	3.0	3.16		
<i>1983</i>							
Faizabad, Uttar Pradesh	5.8	3.6	5.4	2.5	3.1	0.61	1261
Nagina, Uttar Pradesh	2.5	4.2	5.4	2.4	0.7	1.57	599
Ranchi, Bihar	2.3	3.4	5.4	2.1	2.0	0.64	1108
Hazaribagh, Bihar	1.8	2.7	5.4	2.4	1.7	0.12	914
Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh	2.9	2.6	5.4	3.5	2.7	1.00	1504
Rewa, Madhya Pradesh	2.0	2.7	5.4	2.6	1.7	0.48	1263
Bhuaneshwar, Orissa	2.4	1.5	5.4	1.9	1.2	1.15	—
Bankura, West Bengal	1.9	2.1	5.4	1.2	1.5	0.18	916
Hathwara, West Bengal	2.0	2.9	5.4	—	1.3	1.03	898
Karimganj, Assam	4.5	3.7	5.4	2.8	1.9	0.55	—
Titabar, Assam	1.7	1.2	5.4	1.3	0.7	0.73	293
Karjat, Maharashtra	3.4	1.5	5.4	2.7	1.4	0.52	—
Dhaulakuwan, Maharashtra	2.4	3.0	5.4	2.8	1.3	1.12	—
Mean	2.7	2.7	5.4	2.8	1.5		

^a Not grown in 1982.

are sister selections from N22/IR2071-625-252 (IR36), and NDR118 (IET8681) is a selection from IR2071-625-252/Hansraj 'A'. The lines have semidwarf stature and long slender grains. They consistently outyielded the tall local check N22 and the semidwarf national check Cauvery at Faizabad from 1981 to 1983 (Table 1), and are resistant to most foliage diseases. They also were tested at other locations in 1982 and 1983 wet seasons under the All-India Coordinated Rice Improvement Program (AICRIP), and performed better than varieties Akashi and Cauvery (Table 2).

NDR118 is a 95-d variety and thus suitable for rotation with wheat, potato, mustard, and vegetables in north central India. □

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Screening rices for rainfed direct-seeded upland cultivation

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In West Bengal, upland rice depends mostly on premonsoon rain. The cropping season is from Mar to Sep, depending on the onset of premonsoon rains. Average yield is 1.4 t/ha because of the harsh environment and lack of suitable varieties. The following limit crop growth and productivity:

- drought during vegetative phase or ripening,
- weeds,
- difficult fertilizer management because of rapid water percolation, and
- poor recovery after drought.

We screened 18 varieties, with Dular as trial check, for performance under different climatic conditions in 1982-83.

In 1982, most study sites had frequent, severe drought spells in vegetative and

Mean yield and frequency distribution of yield, West Bengal, India.

Variety	Frequency distribution of yield in t/ha						Mean yield (t/ha)
	<1.0	<1.5	<2.0	<2.5	<3.0	>3.0	
<i>1982</i>							
BG367-4	3	2	0	1	1	0	1.3
BG367-7	4	0	0	2	0	1	1.4
B9c-Md-3-3	3	1	1	1	1	0	1.5
BKNLR75091	3	1	1	1	0	1	1.4
CNT-B3-RST-40-2-2							
BW242-5-5	3	1	0	2	1	0	1.5
CR237-1	3	2	1	1	0	0	1.2
Dular	2	2	1	2	0	0	1.5
IET7255	4	1	1	0	1	0	1.2
IET7259	3	0	1	1	1	1	1.8
IR50	2	2	3	0	0	0	1.1
IR9209-47-1-1-6-2	3	1	0	2	1	0	1.4
IR9279-67-3	3	1	0	2	1	0	1.5
IR9708-51-1-2	4	0	1	2	0	0	1.2
IR8608-189-2-2-1-3	3	1	0	1	2	0	1.5
IR13204-24-1-6	3	1	2	1	0	0	1.2
Kiran	2	0	1	3	1	0	1.8
Panke	3	0	1	0	2	1	1.9
Suweon	287	3	1	2	0	0	1.4
Mean							1.4
CD at 5%							0.4
<i>1983</i>							
BG367-4	0	1	3	3	1	1	2.2
BG367-7	1	1	3	1	1	2	2.5
B9c-Md-3-3	1	2	1	2	1	2	2.0
BKNLR75091							
CNT-B3-RST40-2-2	0	3	2	0	1	3	2.3
BW242-5-5	2	2	1	4	0	0	1.7

Cont'd

Variety	Frequency distribution of yield in t/ha						Mean yield (t/ha)
	<1.0	<1.5	<2.0	<2.5	<3.0	>3.0	
CR231-1	1	3	3	0	2	1	1.9
Dular	2	1	1	2	2	1	2.1
IET7255	2	2	2	0	2	1	1.8
IET7259	2	1	2	2	0	2	2.0
IR50	1	1	5	0	0	2	1.8
IR9209-47-1-1-6-2	2	1	3	2	0	1	1.7
IR9729-67-3	2	0	2	2	1	2	2.2
IR9708-51-1-2	1	3	1	4	0	0	1.8
IR8608-189-2-2-1-3	2	1	3	1	1	1	1.7
IR13204-24-1-6	1	3	2	2	1	0	1.7
Kiran	1	3	2	1	0	2	2.1
Panke	1	1	5	0	0	2	2.0
Suweon 287	1	2	3	1	1	1	1.8
Mean							2.0
CD at 5%							0.2

reproductive phases. Panke, an indigenous genotype, yielded an average 1.9 t/ha (see table).

In 1983, the environmental conditions were more favorable. BG367-7 yielded highest, 2.5 t/ha followed by BKNLR-75091 and BG367-4 (see table). Of the varieties tested, Panke, Kiran, and IET7259 had the most stable yields. □

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Evaluation of F₁ hybrids on the Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam

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We evaluated six F₁ hybrids developed at CLRRI in 1984 dry season in a randomized block design with three replications. There were eight 4-m-long rows per plot. Plants were transplanted at 20 × 15-cm spacing, and received 75-26-25 kg NPK/ha.

The F₁ hybrids had negative heterobeltiosis in plant height, panicles/m²,

Table 2. Performance of F₁ hybrids in Oman, Hau Giang, Vietnam, 1984 dry season.

Hybrid and check varieties	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Pan/m ²	Grains /pan	Sterility (%)	1000-g wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
V20A/NN3A (IR36)	93	69	265	76	20.3	31	4.0
Zhen Shan 97 A /NN3A	93	78	263	86	23.2	28	4.9
NN3A	105	90	412	101	17.9	23	5.6
V20A/NN4B (IR42)	97	83	276	77	19.6	30	6.5
Zhen Shan 97 A /NN4B	97	76	277	121	11.5	27	5.6
NN4B	135	86	375	107	16.6	22	4.8
V20A/IR54	95	75	299	79	20.9	31	2.5
Zhen Shan 97 A /IR54	95	76	291	89	22.8	29	2.9
IR54	122	91	361	112	15.8	26	6.0
V20B	97	71	284	74	16.5	30	2.3
97B	103	74	269	97	26.1	28	2.8
CV%		9	17	14	24		15
LSD 5%		10	72	19	6.6		1.1

Table 1. Standard heterosis and heterobeltiosis in yield of F₁ hybrids, Omon, Vietnam, 1984.

Hybrid	Standard heterosis (compared with NN3A)	Heterobeltiosis
V20A/NN4B	+16.45	+33.19
Zhen Shan 97A/NN4B	+0.54	+17.57
Zhen Shan 97A/NN3A	-12.53	-12.53
V20A/NN3A	-33.39	-33.39
Zhen Shan 97A/IR54	-51.75	-51.99
V20A/IR54	-55.81	-58.97

grains/panicle, and sterility and positive heterobeltiosis in 1,000-grain weight (Table 1).

Only V20A/NN4B and Zhen Shan 97A/NN4B performed better than the best parents. They yielded 6.5 and 5.6 t/ha (Table 2). These hybrids had positive standard yield heterosis and heterobeltiosis (Table 1) compared with commercial NN3A. V20A/NN4B and Zhen Shan 97A/NN4B yielded 46% more. Other hybrids did not yield well. Generally, the F₁ hybrids yielded poorly because of a genetic defect in cytoplasmic male

sterile (cms) lines used.

NN4B was a better restorer than NN3A and IR54 for the cms lines V20A and Zhen Shan 97A in Vietnam. □

Harvest index and straw weight of some experimental F₁ rice hybrids

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Crop grain yield is the product of harvest index (HI) and total dry matter. Theore-